

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842
ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue VII, July 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

 @pinagpalapublishing

 pinagpala_publishing

 www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Theory of Caring Touch in Nursing

Krithine Abegail M. Gamiao, MAN, RN

Assistant Professor II

Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology

Nueva Ecija, Region III/Philippines

Abstract

The evolving holistic nursing practice that all aspects of care are being explored and discovered helps in the advancement of nursing science. The Theory of Caring Touch in Nursing was discussed in this paper with the philosophical and theoretical foundation. Caring touch aimed at improving the well-being of a person with an appropriate use by nurses or healthcare giver. The theory of caring touch has the potential to improve the health status of an individual significantly.

Through continuous research in nursing science, most literature supports the assumptions of the theory. But the field of caring touch in nursing reflects the complexity. New ideas and practices may emerge and help more in the practice of nursing. With the use of the theory of caring touch in nursing, health and wellness can be achieved if the nurse has a genuine care for patients.

Keywords: caring touch, nursing, nursing practice, sense of touch

Introduction

In the past years, using the sense of touch in nursing practice has been recognized to promote holistic approach in assisting to heal sick individuals. Touch is one of the first senses to develop in a human being. It is through touch that we are able to interact directly with the world; it is our primary conduit of both pleasure and pain. Touch is our most immediate and powerful sense in the performance of quality nursing care – it is "the first sense" because of the essential role it plays in our experience in the performance of nursing care.

The special facets of touch raise many interesting philosophical and theoretical issues. According to Fulkerson (2014), human touch despite its functional diversity, is a single, unified sensory modality. He also stated the philosophical account of touch, reflecting the interests, methods, and approach that define contemporary philosophy; but his argument is informed throughout by the insights and constraints of empirical work on touch.

Moreover, Fulkerson (2014), also claimed that our intuitive conception of touch comprises a lot of sensory elements that differ so much from one another that it can be

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VII (July 2024), p.13-19 International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

hard to make out the relations among them, or to determine whether they form any truly unitary mode of perception.

Furthermore, the sense of touch is one of the central forms of perceptual experience, though it has often been overshadowed by vision in both philosophy and psychology. The sense of touch often combines the signals with feedback from the muscles and tendons as we actively move and explore the world, and with proprioceptive information about the position of our tactual surfaces. These unique features of touch raise many interesting philosophical issues (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, Touch, 2020).

In addition, the nursing theory of Lydia Hall which is the care, cure, core is the basis of this paper but focuses mainly on care because the care addresses the role of nurses, and is focused on performing the task of nurturing patients. This means the "motherly" care provided by nurses, which may include comfort measures.

The nurse's touch can provide comfort and warmth to sick individuals. They will experience comfort and relief from the pain they experience. A slight touch from the nurse's hand can convey the care or compassion our patients needed for their immediate recuperation.

The sense of touch is really a collection of several senses, encompassing pressure, pain, cold, and warmth. The senses of itch and tickle are related to pressure, and burn injuries are related to pain.

The sense of touch is one of the central forms of perceptual experience, though it has often been overshadowed by vision in both philosophy and psychology. Thought to be one of the first senses to develop, touch occurs across the whole body using a variety of receptors in the skin.

The unique features of touch raise many interesting philosophical issues. In particular, it is a central topic of discussion in debates about the multisensory nature of perception, the relation between perception and action, and the connection between touch and bodily awareness (Fulkerson, 2020).

Philosophical Underpinning

This theory was anchored in the philosophy of Danijela Kambaskovic and Charles T. Wolfe "The Senses in Philosophy and Science: From the Nobility of Sight to the Materialism of Touch". According to Kambaskovic and Wolfe (2014) touch is spread throughout the body and is the least abstract, and therefore basest. Touch may be spread throughout the body, but it is also located in the hand, the focus of worthy and noble human activities. Also, in *The Allegory of Touch*, one of five paintings representing each of the senses, Elizabeth Harvey (2011), has called attention to the hand's crucial role as an organ of touch that bridges mind and body, showing how it oscillates in the image with a more diffuse somatic theme: the protective armor that shields the body from harm. She also quotes that the hand is the "Spokesman of the Body," speaking a universal language that is understood by all. The hand defines the self, as it is impossible to touch without being touched. It takes on the role of a teacher of the mind, both through pleasure, and through the pain that it gives.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Theoretical Framework

Nursing is defined by caring. The Theory of Caring Touch in Nursing is anchored on Jean Watson theory, the Human Caring Theory, wherein the core of the Theory of Caring is that "humans cannot be treated as objects and that humans cannot be separated from self, other, nature, and the larger workforce." The theory is focused on "the centrality of human caring and on the caring-to-caring transpersonal relationship and its healing potential for both the one who is caring and the one who is being cared for" (Watson, 2005).

Description of the Theory of Caring Touch

The Theory of Caring Touch in Nursing explores the holistic nursing practice of human touch approach to healing. In this theory, the act of touching, according to Watson (1975), is an 'intentional physical contact between two or more individuals. The theory help defines what you must do and why you do it.

Theory is a dynamic organizing framework that supports knowledge development and application to practice based on the philosophies of holism, health orientation, person centeredness, and caring (Kim, 2015).

Theories designed to encompass a broad area of science that is Jean Watson's Human Caring Theory is considered grand theory. Middle-range theory is less abstract and deal with a specific phenomenon of practice or research and establish relational statements between concepts that can be described or tested (Butts, 2017).

Assumptions of the Theory

In modern health care, touch – contact between a nurse's hand and a patient – appears to be on its way out. The expanding role of technology in health care, touch as a way of making health assessment is decreasing. In my experience touch can aid the patient attain fast recovery. Despite the rise of robots and other new medical technologies, the nurse's hand remains one of the most valuable nursing tools to aid the patient attain fast recovery. Touch creates a human bond that is particularly needed in this increasingly hands-off, impersonal age. Touch does more than any words to comfort and reassure a patient.

Theory of Caring Touch in Nursing is based on the following assumptions:

1. Nurse and the one being nursed that is the patient, sense of touch will make them in constant interaction with self, others, and the environment.
2. Caring touch enhance and preserve patients worth and dignity.
3. Touch is one way to communicate the knowledge, values and caring actions of the nurse.
4. Caring touch from a nurse makes the practice of nursing unique from other field of profession.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Nursing Metaparadigms

The nursing metaparadigm according to the Theory of Caring Touch in Nursing.

Person

The giver of touch that projects care is the *person* in nursing metaparadigm of this theory. It can be a nurse, someone in the health care team, or it can be a mother that provides the caring touch needed by another person. According to the nursing metaparadigm the human factor or person refers to individuals in a definite culture, family, and society. The nursing metaparadigm of person focuses on the healthcare provider that gives care to patient who is the recipient of caring touch, the patient needed the warmth and tender touch from the healthcare individuals to relieve their pain and so they will feel that they are being cared for (Deliktas, Korukcu, & Aydin, 2019).

Health

The health in nursing metaparadigm of this theory is the degree of wellness of a person or individual. The health or wellness of a person is in constant state of motion, it covers the physical, emotional, intellectual, social and spiritual well-being of a person. Health changes instantaneously, by the mere sense of touch an individual feeling will be changed or improved. This health component of nursing metaparadigm is characterized with multiple dimensions and constantly changing. The theory is that some factors influence the patient's state of well-being, the start of a progress of a good feeling that exudes in a better disposition processes of life.

Environment

The nursing metaparadigm of environment in this theory of caring touch is the space where a social experience happens, it is the setting or context of a person's everyday life that is related to person's health. The environment of a person influences their beliefs that is why societal beliefs, values, mores, customs, and expectations is included in the nursing metaparadigm of environment (Deliktas, Korukcu, & Aydin, 2019).

Nursing

The nursing component of nursing metaparadigm in this theory of caring touch is the actionable side of the three other metaparadigm. In this part of nursing metaparadigm, the nurses i.e. the *person* in this theory, carry out the theory of caring touch, *nursing* an individual or a patient in an *environment* that gives comfort and wellness that emanates an overall feeling of *health*. The actual practice of nursing wherein everything a nurse does for their patient could be included in the nursing of a nursing metaparadigm.

Conclusion

Nursing education, theory, research and clinical practice are the cornerstones of the nursing profession. The relationship of these four cornerstones are reciprocal and cyclical. Clinical practice generates research questions and nursing education guides to formulate knowledge for theory construction. Research guides our clinical practice and

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

nursing education create information to develop theory. The theory guides research and improves clinical practice.

Caring gives nursing its uniqueness hence the reason for nurses to be directly involved in care giving. In this modern technological era, it is still imperative for the nurse to give care to their patients, including tactile massage as a caring tool may create a more holistic approach to caregiving, allowing nurses to act with compassion for both the patient and themselves (Airosa, 2015). The care addresses the role of nurses, and is focused on performing the task of nurturing patients (Gonzalo, 2019). According to Green (2017), touch is the first sense acquired and the last lost and our skin is our largest sensory organ. Touch is highly significant in our everyday encounters, relationships and emotional, social and even physical development

The theory of caring touch in nursing is conceptualize based from the caring act of the nurse. A caring nurse exhibit a caring touch to aid their patients in faster recovery. The caring touch of the nurse will help make patient comfortable. As much as the action might seem small, its significance is great. Furthermore, the sense of touch is a form of non-verbal communication important to establish rapport between the two and changes the perceptions of the patient towards the nurse. Actions such as holding hands, gently stroking the hair are some of the actions that cement the relationship between the nurse and the patient.

Implications

A nurse plays a crucial role in creating a caring and healing environment essential for a patient's recovery. This environment, provided by nurses, significantly aids in the patient's healing process (Nikfarid, Hekmat, & VEDAD, 2018). According to the World Health Organization, health is not just the absence of disease but a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being. Health is dynamic and defined by the client's perception throughout their life (Martino, 2017). This paper argues that optimal health can be achieved through comfort and touch, as posited by Matthew Fulkerson, facilitated by a caring nurse.

Nursing is both an academic discipline and a practice profession, blending the art and science of holistic health care guided by human values such as freedom, choice, and responsibility. Nursing science is developed through theory, research, and analysis, guiding nursing practice through therapeutic interventions. Nurses use critical thinking and clinical judgment to provide evidence-based care across diverse settings, aiming for optimal client wellness (Deliktas, Korukcu, & Aydin, 2019).

Nurses respond professionally to patients' needs, treating them with respect and dignity. Physical care is the most obvious form of this care, including actions like giving back rubs, assisting with mobility, and helping with personal grooming. These actions help patients feel valued and maintain their self-esteem, showing them that their lives continue despite illness. This compassionate care reassures patients that someone is dedicated to their recovery and well-being, fostering a supportive and encouraging environment.

Nursing Education

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Nursing theory serves as the foundation of nursing education. In this rationality, theory of caring touch in nursing is explored based on knowledge from nursing education. It is outlined in important ways from the information in nursing education that will help the nurses to understand its purpose and role in the healthcare setting.

Nursing Research

Research is integral to the theory of caring touch in nursing, this guides the development of many research questions and helps generate, support and strengthen the assumptions of the theory of caring touch in nursing, because all nursing care should be based on research-evidence. Research findings in the use of the theory of caring touch in nursing will be used to develop a protocol and the protocol is followed in daily nursing practice.

Nursing Practice

Holistic nursing practice and has been recognized as a uniquely human approach to healing. Effective nursing practice use critical thinking and current scientific research to facilitate translation or application of knowledge, skills and care to patients in an effective, efficient, and considerate way. Nursing practice with the use of theory of caring touch in nursing can be achieved if the nurse has a genuine care to patients.

References

- Airosa, F. (2015, June 5). *Nurses' and patients' experiences of caring touch interventions in an emergency context*. Retrieved from Karolinska Institutet: <https://openarchive.ki.se/xmlui/handle/10616/44619>
- Bahramnezhad, F., Shiri, M., Asgari, P., & Afshar, P. (2015). A Review of the Nursing Paradigm. *Open Journal of Nursing*, Vol.5 No. 1.
- Butts, J.B. (2017). Components and levels of abstraction in nursing knowledge. In J.B. Butts & K.L. Rich (Eds.), *Philosophies and theories for advanced practice nursing* 3rd ed., pp. 91-112). Burlington, MA: Jones & Bartlett.
- Danijela Kambaskovic-Sawers, Charles Wolfe. *The Senses in Philosophy and Science: From the Nobility of Sight to the Materialism of Touch. A Cultural History of the Senses in the Renaissance*, 2014. fahal-02069998f
- Deliktas, A., Korukcu, O., & Aydin, R. (2019). Nursing Students' Perceptions of Nursing Metaparadigms: A Phenomenological Study. *The journal of nursing research*, 27(5), e45.
- Elizabeth D. Harvey, *The Portal of Touch*, *The American Historical Review*, Volume 116, Issue 2, April 2011, Pages 385–400, <https://doi.org/10.1086/ahr.116.2.385>
- Fulkerson, M. (2014). The First Sense: A Philosophical Study of Human Touch. *Research Gate*, 1-222.
- Gonzalo, A. (2019, September 12). *Lydia Hall: Care, Cure, Core Nursing Theory*. Retrieved from Nurseslabs: <https://nurseslabs.com/lydia-e-halls-care-cure-core-theory/>
- Green, L. (2017). The Trouble with Touch? New Insights and Observations on Touch for Social Work and Social Care. *The British Journal of Social Work*, 773–792.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

- Kim, H.S. (2015). *The essence of nursing practice, philosophy and perspective*. New York, NY: Springer.
- Kuhn, T. (2017). *Structure of scientific revolutions*. Retrieved from Microsoft Word: <https://www.lri.fr/~mbl/Stanford/CS477/papers/Kuhn-SSR-2ndEd.pdf>
- Martino, L. (2017). *Concepts of health and wellbeing*. Retrieved from Health Knowledge: <https://www.healthknowledge.org.uk/public-health-textbook/medical-sociology-policy-economics/4a-concepts-health-illness/section2/activity3>
- Nikfarid, L., Hekmat, N., & Vedad, A. (2018). The main nursing metaparadigm concepts in human caring theory and Persian mysticism: a comparative study. *Journal of medical ethics and history of medicine*, 11, 6.
- Smith, M., & Parker, M. (2015). *Nursing theories and nursing practice (4th ed.)*. Philadelphia, PA: F. A. Davis.
- Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. (2020, November 25). *Touch*. Retrieved from Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy: <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/touch/>
- The College of New Jersey. (2020, August 5). *Metaparadigm Concepts*. Retrieved from The College of New Jersey: <https://nursing.tcnj.edu/about/meta-concepts/>
- Watson, J. (2008). *Nursing: The philosophy and science of caring (Revised ed.)*. Louisville, CO: University Press of Colorado.
- Watson, J. (2005). Caring science as a sacred science. In McEwen, M. and Wills, E. (Ed.). *Theoretical basis for nursing*. USA: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Watson, W.H. (1975) 'The meanings of touch: geriatric nursing', *Journal of Communication*, **25** 104–10.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.12730311

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.